

**POSTCOLONIAL ‘ARIEL’: AN ETHICAL MAP OF ACHIEVED AND LOST RESPONSES IN
THE MAKING OF AN AUTHOR**

Dr. Ramesh Sharma, Department of English, Assam Don Bosco University, Assam

ABSTRACT:

Character of Caliban from Shakespearan play *The Tempest* has, as Fauzia Mustafa endorses, has often been used in the postcolonial writings as a literary “architype”. Caliban, as far as an exploited character, exploited by Prospero who has been understood as a colonial figure, can be a postcolonial representation. However, as the play demonstrates, he is not a creative figure. Considered this, the archetype has a very derogatory sense when it is applied to the postcolonial representation. Therefore, it is an urgent imperative to identify a new archetype that best accommodates the creative and intellectual postcolonial representations. Caliban can only be the archetype of exploitation. The creative and artistic force in the postcolonial writings can be best represented by the figure of Ariel in the same play and this can be best validated by V.S. Naipaul. His writings and responses to them can show how he has attended to the Ariel attribute. Literary reputation of V.S. Naipaul is, contentiously though, immeasurable. He has been immensely praised for the literary brilliance and contribution with a series of prizes. He has been honored with the Booker Prize, the W. H. Smith Prize, the Hawthorn den Prize, the Bennett Prize, the T. S. Eliot Award, knighthood and the Noble Prize in 2001. But he is also equally indicted for being not honest in representation, particularly from the eastern world. Accordingly, he gets a huge critical response to both his travel writings and fictions. But the response has, as Fawzia Mustafa observes, “...radically divergent views, dependent on the perspective of the reader (1)” and hence it tends to become paradoxical. It is paradoxical in two senses. Firstly, it senses, and eventually takes the attribute of, the paradoxical postcolonial subject matter that Naipaul explores, represents, and gives a rhetorical bent. Secondly, the “divergent views” cancel out each other’s observation on Naipaul and thus become contradictory. This clash of perceptions in deed establishes him to the literary platform of the international repute where he tends to assume an “Ariel” role, the spirit, a symbol of creative power that can negotiate with discordant elements in the Shapeapearen play *The Tempest* in contrast to the always-complaining and revengeful subjugated bestial figure Caliban, the “literary archetype” of many of the postcolonial writings.

Key-words: paradox, Ariel, Caliban, archetype, postcolonial

INTRODUCTION :

The Nobel Laureate of 2001, V.S. Naipaul, was born in the Caribbean Islands and later migrated to the United Kingdom and took British citizenship. His grandfather was an Indian who migrated to the Caribbean Islands as an indentured labour under the colonial British administration in the Nineteenth century. Naipaul started writing in Nineteen fifties and gradually earns a global readership. He is one of the most read postcolonial writers and an exclusive representation of the postcolonial world- culture, history, people, politics, religion. He not only earns a global readership but also critical responses, often lethal. There are two types of responses, referred to as “paradoxical” above, that Naipaul gets and they can be studied under two general categories: achieved and lost. The achieved response has orientation towards a rigorous interpretation of a text- an idea that origins and evolves while reading a work. It is achieved in the sense that a critical rigor is the general expectation for a text because its entire fecundity rests on it. A text lives only by this response. Whereas, the lost response focuses on writers, even on their personal backgrounds, is filled with prejudice, anxiety, and contempt or in short governed by

subjective elements. Textual interpretation for opening up possibilities and significances becomes a secondary matter for it. This paper will consider first the achieved response to Naipaul with an assumption that its concern is with the interpretation of his writings that predominantly represent the “third world,” or the world “outside” that he refers to in his Noble Lecture, 2001, once ravaged by the Western empire; and then the lost response with the conjecture that it is subjective in nature and personally obsessive with contempt and scathing attack on the author accused of being bias in the representation of the subject matter.

Fawzia Mustafa has a brilliant observation of Naipaul in which he deviates from the conventional archetypes of postcolonial representation of a colonized. He writes that,

The ambivalence bred of functioning in a subordinated relation to the "language of the oppressor" has been to a large extent the central crisis informing much postcolonial and Caribbean writing. The figure of Caliban is of course the literary archetype evoked to exemplify this phenomenon, but... at least one writer thought the figure of Ariel best represented the Creole relationship to the Old World. Naipaul's writing positions him as an Ariel figure... (220)

To understand the idea of “Ariel Naipaul” in the light of the extract, this paper seeks to draw the idea of “ethics” or being “ethical” from Emanuel Levinas, which according to Bharati Mukherjee “is about unhousing and remaining unhoused and at the same time free” (5). In other words, “ethics” implies endorsement of the inevitability of the presence of an absence in a presence and presence of the presence in the absence to understand the significance of an existence, which in this context is the creative author V.S. Naipaul.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To discuss the achieved response
2. To discuss the lost response
3. To argue how both the responses become an enabling phenomenon for Naipaul

ACHIEVED RESPONSE:

Bruce King perhaps stands forefront in the first category of the response, others being Helen Heyward, Vijay Mishra and Rob Nixon. These responses, however, form the ethical counterpart to the lost responses. In the process of detail observation of the galaxy of texts in *V.S. Naipaul* (1993), Bruce King emphasizes on a note on paradox in the ‘Introduction’ that underlines the basic framework of the entire corpus of Naipaulean works. He opines that Naipaul’s

...views often have the effect of paradox and surprise forcing a re-examination of received opinions. He objects that describing him as a West Indian writer is patronizing and limiting. A severe critic of India...he is also a nationalist who feels humiliated by the weakness and exploitation of the colonized; he blames European imperialism for the problems it left its former colonies, while praising it for bringing peace and modern thought to areas of the world that remained medieval and debilitated by continual local wars. There is a moral honesty in his work, a refusal to sentimentalize England or the former colonies. (02)

With few examples -being West Indian and not being so, being a critic and nationalist, justifying and condemning the imperialism at the same time -King strikes on the very functional area of Naipaul’s thinking, a cerebral gymnastic for ideas between uneven ends that governs his narratives. And the same idea is carried over to the subsequent chapters. The second chapter ‘*Miguel Street, The Mystic Masseur and The Suffrage of Elvira*’ focuses on the Trinidadian trilogy which are set during the transitional phase, 1930s, and are more pertinent as exploration of ‘social history’ not for a serious ‘analytical perspective’ as in Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka but meant more for amusement. The *Miguel Street* is concerned with ‘improbability of achievement’ from the inhabitants of the ‘impoverished’ locales of

Port of Spain who are plagued by chaotic transitional cultural underbelly, mimicry, corruption and illiteracy as the colonial legacy. Achievement in such a context is only a probable impossibility; it ends in pretention. Therefore, King adds, “In *Miguel Street* nothing is made, no business succeeds, no art work is finished, no love or marriage lasts (18)” even though they are claimed. It implies that the narrative is also an odd story, a sub-text, between pretense for achievement and a grotesque reality of not being qualified for in the absence of higher educational institutions at the time except a few schools, and as an effect inability of the mass to grasp few of the available coveted foreign scholarships. It’s a land of mind without substance trying for excellence manifested in the comical characters like Bogart, Morgan and Man-man.

Likewise, *Suffrage of Elvira*, according to King, also does not share the analytical perspective. It is set in 1950s general election in which people have started seeing a ‘possibility.’ The word ‘possibility’ is ironically loaded. As unfolded in the process of election, the moral corruption on the part of the people in Elvira surfaces in between the lines. Buying votes of ethnic communities, paying for funerals, food and drink, bribing candidates for work etc. are the possibilities from the election that Elvira understand. There is no possibility beyond bribery. There is nothing that regulates the election; there is no control centre to balance the election for social benefits. Mr. Surujpat Harbans, the protagonist, wins the election and ends his electioneering with the contempt “Elvira, you is a bitch!” indirectly detaching him from all his future engagement with Elvira. The end of the election is ironically personal, balanced in terms of loss and gain. King thus comments,

At the conclusion the winners and losers are what individuals have gained and lost in relation to each other in the course of events connected to the election: 'Chittaranjan lost a son-in-law and Dhaniram lost a daughter-in-law. Elvira lost Lorkhoor and Lorkhoor won a reputation. (33)

Therefore, King observes the narrative is an amusing social or literary comedy. For him it is the “last of Naipaul's entertainments, social comedies of the incongruities of colonial Trinidad (35).” However, with the subsequent fictions the distance between the illusion and reality gets narrowed and the comedy is more and more replaced by seriousness, anger, anxiety, dream and desire.

In the third chapter ‘*A House for Mr. Biswas* and *The Middle Passage*’, King observes the expression of the central vision of Naipaul: question of life and existence. What Naipaul envisages of the actual reality and what it appears to be are virtually contradictory. In King’s understanding, the narrative does not simply have a postcolonial concentration; Trinidad being the site, its appeal is universal. He writes, “Here [in *A House for Mr. Biswas*] is the central vision that finds expression in Naipaul's language of order, disorder, extinction, void, and which influences the way he looks at society, politics and culture (37)” which are not exclusively “third world” specific. In this sense the narrative can also be read as an aesthetic engagement into and dramatization of a universal vision that sharply contradicts the world in appearance, Trinidad and its socio-cultural context being the sites. Naipaul envisions the world, according to King, “...as without purpose, violent, dangerous... fearful, comfortless, irrational and brutal (37).” Societies are organized for protection of individuals and one who is out of them has chances to get plunged in the void as exemplified by Mr. Biswas, the protagonist, in the narrative. The stronger and more resourceful societies are the more chances for their individuals to get saved from the null and void.

In the travel writing *An Area of Darkness* as elaborated in the fourth chapter ‘*Mr. Stone and the Knights Companion* and *An Area of Darkness*,’ King opines that Naipaul inclines towards and reacts against the traditional Indian idea of ‘fatalism.’ It is also a writing that operates between memory India and real India in which the former suddenly but paradoxically collapses when exposed to the later. It is rather a discovery of how Indians have lost themselves into “absurdities and foolish mysteries,” and how the “decayed” old India mixes up with the modern limiting India from becoming what Naipaul had fancied.

What he expects but cannot find in Indians, according to King, is that a "...a will to change, an idea of the self, a purpose, an existential being which is authentic in evolving from the past and the culture (64)." In this sense the narrative can also be read as an attempt on the part of the author to revisit to his dreamt root and a revealing that, contradictorily, he cannot return to that as he feels more humiliated and frustrated by the India that he discovers. Yet, his initial perception of India defers in his latter travel narratives.

India: A Million Mutinies Now that figures in the chapter 9 '*Finding the Centre, The Enigma of Arrival, A Turn in the South and India: A Million Mutinies*', according to King, is a part of Naipaul's continuous exploration of the "paradox of freedom" (152) in India. This time, after twenty-seven years of his first visit, the narrative manifests another face of India intellectually evolving, coming into sense from the absurdities and superstitions and now with a developing central economy governed by natives, unlike that he had observed before. The narrative is also a discovery of how idea of freedom has gradually moved from the elite class to broader range of societies and how it has been much more realized now than before. The change that figures now after twenty-seven years, according to King, is that "A notion of India has been restored, after having been lost for centuries... (152)." The narrative is about seemingly improbable possibilities, reliable and credible for the future, India has shown within a very short span of time.

In the fifth chapter '*A Flag on the Island, The Mimic Men and The Loss of Eldorado*' King thinks that *The Mimic Men* intertwines two themes in which a sense of freedom from and engagement with the roots conflict each other. He says, "Singh attempts to be free, to construct his own identity, but keeps returning to the question of whether he is a product of his racial, colonial, educational and family past (75)." As a politician, Ralph Sing eventually does not return from England and rather chooses to look for a new identity after leading a delegation there for financial aid indicating that he opts freedom from the hounding anarchy back at Isabella, his place of origin. It is at this stay he begins to memoir his life in England and in the process, he has to return to his origin, his childhood memory, his previous visit to and return from England and marriage with Sandra, short but successful real estate business at Isabella and successful but catastrophic political career. Thus, the new identity of Ralph also endorses the presence of what he was.

The eighth chapter "'A New King for the Congo' and *A Bend in the River*" opens up with a different note. The narrative is underlined by an apocalyptic vision for those who have become homeless in the previous colonies and in general restated by an urgency to struggle for survival being rational. Either for the protagonist Salim, who is an outsider-insider and Indian by roots in the bend of the river or Zabeth, a woman from the depth of Africa and her son Ferdinand, the life is doomed. Salim narrowly escapes death at the end sandwiched between the tribal war, between the Big Man who mimics European orders and those who love to return to their ancestry. Zabeth never feels secured and always pricks her ear towards probable dangers enroute between her village and the bend in the river. Thus, King writes, "It is perhaps Naipaul's most pessimistic novel, filled with a sense of apocalypse, of the futility and vanity of life, of an impending worldwide disaster and coming of a new dark age... (119)", or in short a "symbolic wasteland." The narrative becomes a metaphor: if every bit of life heading towards the "dark age" is what the text is about, there is a subtext raising an alarm for rationality, an imperative critical response to the danger, as only the salvation.

Helen Heyward in his book *The Enigma of V.S. Naipaul: Sources and Contexts* is interested in examination of the use of raw material in Naipaul mostly found in his autobiographical sources and travel reports. In his earlier fictions, he extensively uses figure of his father as material. Heyward draws parallel between Seepersad, the father of Naipaul, and Mr. Biswas, the protagonist in *A House for Mr. Biswas* and Pundit Ganesh, the mystic, in *The Mimic Men* in terms of their aspiration for writing. Mr.

Biswas is a journalist and Ganesh aspires to be a writer though he does not succeed. Also, the critic finds parallel between the father of Ralph Singh in *The Mimic Men* and Seepersad. Singh's father was a political and religious leader and this influences the political career, though short lived, of Ralph Singh, like Seepersad influences Naipaul's literary career. But the fictional portrayal of his father, according to the critic, "manifests an Oedipal ambivalence in its treatment (11)." He makes Ganesh rather a clown giving a satirical bent to the representation and towards the end of the *A House for Mr. Biswas*, Anand, the son of Biswas, refuses to see him even in his death bed. At one point of time Naipaul confirms his father as model, as quoted by Hayward, "My father was extremely important in my childhood: nearly everything that I am because of this great link I felt with him, and a lot of my work — especially my early work — I meant to be dedicated to him (1)" but other times he detaches: "I never had a model that I wanted to become. I am not aware of other styles of writing. I do my own. I write in my own way. I have no models (11)." Attachment and oedipal detachment with his father as inspiration constitutes much of the enigma as a narrative theme in Naipaul.

In the chapter 4 'Naipaul's changing representation of India: autobiographical and literary backgrounds' Heyward suggests that the material India Naipaul experiences in the Indian trilogy that he receives through travel writings and as recollection from memory, is shaped by a tension between "...a sense of the personality of the writer and with autobiographical detail (Hayward 111)." His visit to India was full of expectations to know more about himself knowing his roots: "And though in India I am a stranger, the starting point of this inquiry — more than might appear in these pages — has been myself (111)." But no sooner he lands on the country the memory India fades; the expectation collapses and he is left out "touched with fear (116)" to discover brutality in Indian as his root. Negotiation becomes almost impossible for him. Nevertheless, he considers the same material in the subsequent works in a span of decade each until he is convinced with its scope in the last travel. But the treatment from the first to last is always affected by a tussle between his personality, his reaction to the shock from the unexpected, and the terror India as the home of his ancestor. Thus, the critic summarily writes, "His writings on India can be viewed as a site for the playing out of the tensions caused by his personal and ancestral involvement with the country (141)." The trilogy is an experience between expectation, shock and their reversal.

Chapter six 'Images of Africa and Europe in *A Bend in the River*' considers the figuration of the two continents in the narrative in reference. It is suggested that Africa figures as in European literature, dark and evil, and the Europe as something that has lost its significance. He says the narrative has an influence from *A Congo Diary* that records Naipaul's travels in Zaire in 1975. Africa is used "as the negation of European civilization, the site of a reversion to savagery, where human brutality is exposed in the raw (172)." However, Europe also does not figure ideal; it is used as having lost its grandeur, order and attraction. The narrative eventually ends in a terror. The situation gets tensed under the difference in opinion between the Big Man who wants a European model of governance and accordingly uses force to tame people. On the other hand, a faction of people opts for ancestral ideal, rejects Big Man, and accordingly regresses to traditional past. The confrontation grows detrimental; it is detrimental both for the Europeans or who prefer everything Europeans and African as well. Ferdinand, the son of Zabeth from the interior Africa, says in regards to the rebels, as quoted by Hayward "They're going to kill everybody who can read and write, everybody who ever put on a jacket and tie... They're going to kill and kill. They say it is the only way, to go back to the beginning before it is too late (176)." In other words, killing of everybody in "jacket and tie" becomes emancipation. Literally, Europe is received with brutality. Killing of the Father Huismans, the Belgian headmaster is a clear indication that Europe and the European have already lost their attraction in Africa. What is evidenced by the use of Europe and Africa is that Naipaul takes an ambivalent position: he accepts the colonial model of Africa but rejects the empire.

Vijay Mishra in *Literature of the Indian Diaspora: Theorizing the Diasporic Imaginary* (2007), chapter 3, while working for a theoretical framework for the study of Diasporas, undertakes a task to study the works of Naipaul as trauma stricken, that is to say he endeavours to explore his works as an expression that "...bears the traces of an original trauma (106)" of departure from homeland. Trauma literally means a state of an emotional shock from a physical or external injury. It remains repressed in human mind and can be revisited through the agency of memory. As a methodology drawing upon the idea of "new historicism" from Stephen Greenblatt- the idea of historicity of a text and textuality of the history- Mishra attempts to locate an intertextuality between the Naipaulean texts and the history of indentured Indian labour in Trinidad, who were taken there by the British in the early part of the twentieth century. The literal transposition from India to Trinidad and the exotic world the indentured labours encounter there translate into an emotional shock, a trauma for them. It never escapes their memory and desire for returning to India either literally or in terms of its values. India as a pervasive setting never figures in the fictions that concern Trinidad; they are all about the Indians and Trinidadians creole. Neither the characters are always obsessed with the idea of home.

Nevertheless, sometimes in terms of choice, India and Indianness always prevail. For instance, in the *A House for Mr. Biswas* Mr. Biswas is considered for the job of sign painting in the Hanuman House "only because he was an Indian (*A House for Mr. Biswas*, 82)." Further, in a casual instance without much emphasis towards the end of the fiction, the narrator informs us that haunted by the memory of the homeland, Tulsis have never fully settled in Trinidad:

...the Tulsis had never considered themselves settled in Arwacas or even Trinidad. It was no more than a stage in the journey that had begun when Pundit Tulsi left India. Only the death of Pundit Tulsi had prevented them from *going back to India*, and ever since they had talked, though less often than the old men who gathered in the arcade every evening, of moving on, to Indi (*A House for Mr. Biswas* 412, emphasis added).

But nowhere, the Tulsis expose a similar will. However, it is clear then the pull of the memory is there even though the concern of the narrative is explicitly the life in Trinidad. On the contrary, the unfulfilled desire for literal "going back to India" by Tulsis is compensated by Naipaul himself in his triple trips. As explored before, the first visit to India is no less than a traumatic shock for him being exposed to the real India as against his dream India. Here as an Indian of Trinidad, Naipaul can be seen sharing the trauma of Tulsis. His first impression is that he does not belong to India; neither India belongs to him, another instance of getting lost. The lost homeland occasionally recalled in the narrative like *A House for Mr. Biswas* interacts with the history of three generations of Indian Diasporas [autobiographically the history of the father of Mr. Biswas, himself and his generation] which suffers emotional pain conditioned by a sense of becoming displaced, rootless, exiled, ambivalent and getting lost between India and the Caribbean Island. Mishra concludes that the narrative "...carries the trauma of the original departure, the trauma of plantation life in the very interstices of language, in the aesthetic design ... (132)" of Naipaul as a sub-text which is indicated by the memory of India in many of the characters cited before. More the memory more is the indication of trauma as its cause.

In *London Calling: V.S. Naipaul, Postcolonial Mandarin* Rob Nixon attempts to probe into how Naipaul gets a huge acceptance and readership in Europe and America despite arousing a huge indignation in the "third world" - Africa, Caribbean, Arab and India. In the West he is honoured with a galaxy of accolades. He is referred to as "Delphic oracle" (Nixon 04) by the critic King John¹, alluding to the classical Greek oracle of Delphi who is supposed to be all knowing and having authority over all future. Whereas in the "third world," he is lampooned. Nixon catalogues the evocation of the former colonies by Naipaul in different contexts as "... 'barbarous,' 'primitive,' 'tribal,' 'simple,' 'irrational,' 'static,' 'without history,' 'futureless,' 'bush,' 'philistine,' 'sentimental,' 'parasitic,' and 'mimic' (6)." He

anecdotes that in a West Indian literary convention a participant, passion running high, even “volunteered to shoot (4)” Naipaul. He is accused as the defender of the “white race.” In short, there is a paradox of absolute acceptance on the one side and reciprocal rejection on the other in the former colonies out of which the reputation of Naipaul intriguingly flowers.

Nixon thinks there are other ways around too. He traces the drives of Naipaul’s achieved authority over the imperial West in his early life. His father Seepersad Naipaul is his inspiration. He was destined to become a pundit with religious education. However, he deviated from this profession to choose the noble profession of writing. In that context, he did not have formal education; neither had he forerunners and models as inspiration. His commitment for writing, nevertheless, was always running high. Gradually he became a freelance contributor to the *Trinidad Guardian*. And under such a tragic literary commitment, he published the book *Gurudeva and Other Indian Tales* in 1943. It steered many of the writers in Trinidad to see writing as a promising career. And according to Nixon, the same year Naipaul, who was just eleven “...determined to become a writer (8).” Despite the attempt, the commitment of Seepersad could not find full expression given his circumstances. Thus, it can be seen that Naipaul’s entire corpus of writing is also compensation to and the salvation of the unfulfilled commitment of his father towards writing profession. But it is still risky to fully agree that Naipaul’s writing is the compensation. The stories of his father were the representation of rural Indian peasants in Trinidad whose values and assumptions had been carried over from India. Contrarily, Naipaul’s writings about Trinidad, and also of other locations, are primarily marked with anger and anxiety of a larger world beyond his paternal domain. Naipaul was born and brought up in Trinidad in a highly individualistic and engulfing family which, for instance, finds a figurative treatment in *A House for Mr. Biswas*. It is a creole society. His father too was subject to the same engulfment in Trinidad which to a large extent contradicted and limited the flowering of literary genius in him. He did not get a desired literary audience. Therefore, according to Nixon, Naipaul’s determination for writing “...was mingled with revenge, as he nursed an unrequited and ultimately disfiguring anger against the place that had shamed the nobility of his father’s ambitions (10).” Therefore, what is evidenced by Nixon is that Naipaul gets the drive from his father and the subject matter that shares the attributes of a modern society from his early experience and understanding of the Caribbean world. This draws the attention of the western readers finding their parallels in Naipaul and obliquely it helps him to assume authority over them.

Nixon does not see only the paternal influence as a reason for his authorial achievement. Based primarily on his non-fictions, which according to him are widely received than the fictions, he is also interested in looking Naipaul from political angle. He says that,

The vigor of the debates sparked by Naipaul’s work, the tendency of his polemical style to restoke those debates, together with his eminent position as a literary influence on British and American understanding of the postcolonial era, have ensured that he is no longer simply viewed as a writer, but as embodying a set of politically charged ideas about Third World-First World relations. (14)

His non-fictions, for instance, *The Middle Passage*, *Masque of Africa*, *An Area and Darkness* and *India: A Wounded Civilization* are set in Caribbean, Africa and India primarily at the time of their independence. Therefore, they sense much of the political twists and turns, the political shift from the imperial to the native system of governance and its ramifications. In the first chapter, Nixon explores that Naipaul establishes himself as an ‘exile’ or ‘immigrant’ or an outsider in front of his audience in his travels which are undertaken at the time of political turmoil. Nixon quotes from Charles Michener who says that “Naipaul is, of all the great writers of exile, the most rootless, the least fortified by the tradition in which he writes (Nixon 17)” and another from Leon Gottfried who observes that “‘home’ can never ultimately be more than the books he writes or, perhaps more precisely, the action of writing them (17).” Simply put, Naipaul gets established as a pathetic, homeless therefore deserving care person who

straightway finds a place in the heart of the Western critic. In the second chapter, Nixon points out that Naipaul gets the attestation of the western scholars by sharing the Victorian travel writings' obsession with racism. For instance, in *The Middle Passage* Naipaul uses an epigraph before the beginning and also in the first chapter from James Anthony Froude's book *The English in the West Indies* (1887). The book, according to Nixon, is "...the most shrilly racist of Caribbean travel books (45)," therefore beginning a book in Froude by Naipaul is a reverence to the European racism and a confirmation of it as a welcome legacy.

In the third chapter, Nixon explores that Naipaul establishes a "hybrid" identity -a racist defending European intellectual tradition and an "exile"- a "quasi-global identity that contains both First and Third worlds (15)" to secure an affectionate space in the western readership. In the fourth chapter, the Nixon shows Naipaul's reverence to Joseph Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* and its ramification in the exploration of Africa in the works like *Masque of Africa*. Naipaul himself claims that Conrad, as quoted by Nixon from 'Conrad's Darkness' (1980), "...had been everywhere before me (15)." It can be seen then the exploration of Africa in the travel writing [also in *A Bend in the River*] is informed by the view of Conrad's protagonist Marlow and while paying this reverence to one of the representative modern English novelists, Naipaul succeeds in domiciling himself in the English literary tradition. In the fifth chapter, Nixon explores the rationale behind the use of terms like "... primitive, simple society, colonial, mimicry, and parasitism with a great deal of explanatory power (17)" by Naipaul. With the use of the term "primitive" Naipaul obliquely brings it in contrast with the idea of civilized society and with the others he attempts to erase the cultures of colonial societies, according to Nixon. In both the attempts, he shares an imperial design and thus comes in loyal proximity with the Western world. The sixth chapter examines the politics behind constant use of the term "mimicry" by Naipaul in relation to colonial societies. The term triggers a sense of dependence which Nixon calls a life of "mimic dependency." Mimicry for Naipaul, according to him, is the function of previous colonies and not the function of the empire; it is, paradoxically speaking, "...a form of colonialism from below... (132)." Therefore, it is clear that Naipaul with the politics in the use of "mimicry" shifts the blame from empire to the colonies making themselves accountable for their plight and as a reward the empire acknowledges him with its readership.

LOST RESPONSE:

Some writings that make appearance in journals and magazines from the perspective of the eastern readership seriously censure Naipaul, as highlighted by Rob Nixon, accusing him of being a hater of Islam or the natives and politically defending the western ideology of racism in his writings. Wendy O'Shea-Meddour, Golam Gaus Al-Quaderi and Md. Habibullah, Haidar Eid, Mohammad Bakari, Edward Said and Derek Walcott seem to appropriate this response, yet they should be understood as ethical to the first responses. Wendy O'Shea-Meddour critiques Naipaul particularly on two of his travel narratives *Among the Believers* and *Beyond Belief* as "orientalist excursion among the converted people." In her writing she argues that "... his standing as an authority on the Muslim world needs to be reconsidered (58)." Picking up the same narratives, two critics Golam Gaus Al-Quaderi and Md. Habibullah jointly attack the travelogue *Beyond Belief: Islamic Excursion Among the Converted People* (1998) for his remark on the Muslim, "Islam is in its origin an Arab religion. Everyone not an Arab who is a Muslim is a convert" (Prologue to *Beyond Belief*). They censure him as "plagued by limitation of vision, orientalist ideas, islamophobia, prejudice and misconceptions (23)." The writers dump his themes as "rudimentary, primitive, unsatisfactory and concocted (34)." His ideas, according to them, are

baffled by his limited vision and prejudice of Islam, therefore they need re-orientation. However, both the claims recoil back to themselves as they do not take into consideration the freedom of expression of a liberal writer.

Haidar Eid catches Naipaul on *A Band in the River* and does not agree with his representation of Africa and Africans in it. Within the aesthetic realm of the narrative, he argues, Naipaul has a politics of defending the empire. In other words, Haider sees him as political, not in the literal sense of the word rather he means to suggest that there is a difference between what is shown and seen in the fiction. He represents the African society as broken, unstable and the Africans unable to reshape it as they lack in creative potential and thus at the backdrop indirectly hints the need of an external power to govern them. Instead of inviting Africans, Haider further accuses, to depend on their power and “motivating them to seek an alternative by proceeding on the basis of their own concrete reality, cultural heritage and history without losing the straightforward movement, Naipaul offers no solutions (Eid 12).” Contrary to all the censors, Sanjeev Kumar sees Naipaul in terms of the narrative *A Band in the River* as authenticating different theoretical terms defined by Homi K. Bhabha in his book *The Location of Culture*. Besides being anything else, the narrative is the attestation of mimicry, hybridity and ambivalence. Given this, the narrative must be working with all these postcolonial ironies and contradictions that the emerging world encounters. In fact, the entire corpus of post-colonial writings moves around the themes of mimicry, hybridity and ambivalence, but the critic thinks that they get special emphasis in Naipaul. Thus, Kumar writes the narrative “validates the theoretical base provided by Homi K. Bhabha in his *The Location of Culture*... (122).”

Perception on Naipaul often transcends the postcolonial paradox and takes into account a revision of history so as to come to a conclusion to understand how a presence is altered by the past. In his later fiction *Magic Seeds* Naipaul takes up the issue of Peasants’ Movements in India and how they have a nexus with urban naxalites and why they remain still unresolved (Naxalite’s Movement is still an issue in India). Plight of peasant or the servile class has a historical reason which, however, has always been by-passed by the main stream of historiography thus misleading their emancipation movements. Santwana Haldar takes up this case in *Magic Seeds* to explore the agrarian society and its yet unspoken history of servility in one of the seminal essays ‘V.S. Naipaul’s India in *Magic Seeds: A Close View of Post-Colonial Indian Society*.’ To know the existing condition of peasants, their oppression and their protest, Naipaul peeps into the history of making of them a servile class. According to Haldar, in terms of Willie’s experience, Naipaul “traces the origin of oppression to the caste system in Hindu India” (89), the same carried over by the Islamic invasion and eventually by the British Empire. In *Magic Seeds*, Joseph, a rebel reveals to Willie an event that can be taken as an example of many such, in the history of the making and strengthening of the servility, which Haldar considers as evidence:

All the land in India is a scared. But here we are on especially sacred ground. We are on the site of the last great Indian kingdom, and it was the sight of a catastrophe. Four hundred years ago the Muslim invaders ganged up on it and destroyed it...They killed the priests, the philosophers, the artisans, the architects, the scholars...The only people they left behind were the serfs in the villages, and they parceled them out among themselves...The serfs in the village policed themselves...Some ran before and after the horses of their lords. Some did the scavenging. Some dig the grave digging. Some offered their women. All of them referred to themselves as slaves...After four hundred years of this kind of rule the people here would have grown to believe that this was their eternal condition. (37-38)

The invasion was an apocalyptic event in the ancient history of India; all the men of talents were annihilated in the “great Indian kingdom” [the Vijananagara Kingdom in the south] and only the serfs were spared to turn them into “slaves.” The condition of the serfs did not improve even after the British takeover. They divided the Indians into two general categories: martial and servile races. The former

was recruited in British army, the later remained unchanged. However, after the revolt of 1857, according to Haldar, the martial class “degraded” as British stopped recruiting them. Gradually this class metamorphosed into the servile. Even with the independence, the servile class was sustained and carried over. And in these centuries of foreign domination, Haldar writes, “Indian people quickly forgot their past and believed in what they were told, as the idea of history was denied to them (90).” However, besides the two classes, according to Haldar, there used to be the elite class (from aristocratic and their relative’s family) who benefitted a lot from the domination. They had no problem with foreign rules. With independence, gradually the descendents of the old lords who oppressed the servile class settled in urban cities to do odd jobs. They picked up ideas of foreign revolutionary movements and brought them back home making the principles of the so-called Naxalite’s Movements which are fully controlled by them. Kandapalli in the narrative, a village school master is such a character who dreamt of making a revolution uniting such descendants of the old lords but eventually fails. The irony with such movements is that the poor peasants for whom they are supposed to work “did not share their views (92).” The means and the end of the Peasants’ Movement, therefore, do not match. Many of the rebels that Willie comes across do not know for whom they are fighting. Hence, they remain unresolved in India.

Mohammad Bakari in his writing ‘V.S. Naipaul: From Gadfly to Obsessive’ while trying to attempt a real estimate periodizing Naipaul’s works into the mid-sixties, the seventies and the eighties eventually loses his track and takes a subjective bent. The thrust of the essay is to consider Naipaul’s personal life, his marriage of first an English wife and a Muslim next into its framework and to show its social implication. Bakari believes that with the marriages Naipaul attempts to dominate both the “colonial oppressor” and the “other”:

It is paradoxical that Naipaul, on the death of his English wife, should choose for a new wife, a Pakistani of Muslim background. The desire to marry an English wife and, later, a Muslim wife, in *Freudian parlance*, could be a reflection of the repressed unconscious desire on his part to dominate the colonial oppressor and the symbolic “other”, the British and the Muslim (247, emphasis added).

In addition, drawing Naipaul into the “Freudian parlance” or by attempting a psychoanalysis of his marriage, Bakari runs the risk of orienting his work more towards the personal desire of the writer because in the Freudian theory of psychoanalysis, an individual and not a social whole predominates. This is also the reason why C.J. Jung, a protégée of Freud, departs from Freud accusing him of being too individual in his analysis and relates the individual psychology to a “mass consciousness. Bakari dehumanizes Naipaul with bestiality in the choice of “gadfly” as the dominating image for him. In his concluding remark he writes, Naipaul has eventually “metamorphosed from a gadfly to an obsessive (259)” and assuming authority over the world readership, claims that his entire works will “be consigned to the dustbin of literary history (258).” This is nothing but a spillover of his antagonism. Bakari censures Naipaul that he is biting and too critical of Muslims and Africans, their culture and religion on the one hand and too much “obsessive” of the Hinduism on the other. Bakari even accuses him of espousing ideology of “BJP in India”, Hinduism, which he condemns as “exclusionary [that] allows no room for those from other ethnic or racial groups (250)” and denounces the Hindu religion as “watertight.” But Bakari totally remains oblivious of the basic Vedantic philosophy of Hinduism, the philosophy of “Vasudaiva Kutumbakam” or the acceptance of the world as a single family. What is evident in Bakari, therefore, is that he paradoxically takes the same subjective bent which he censures in Naipaul.

Edward Said who attempts a discursive textual analysis of the colonial discourses [discourse in Foucauldian sense] to arrive at the idea of orientalism and by implication and extension the entire fabric of the postcolonial studies/theories contradictorily to his own authority takes a very personal analysis of Naipaul in his otherwise seminal book *Reflection on Exile and Other Essays* when he prescribes him the

bestial image of a “scavenger.” Commenting on the politics of the travel narrative *Among the Believers: An Islamic Journey*, which is the outcome of his travels into Iran, Pakistan, Malaysia and Indonesia between 1979-80, Said points out two aspects of Naipaul for condemnation. According to him, in the narrative “Naipaul the writer flows directly into Naipaul the social phenomenon (126).” The first Naipaul has a “silent presence” in the narrative, and second Naipaul is active throughout the book to explore “Islamic weakness;” Naipaul as a writer is vain, therefore he is forced to be the phenomenon to cover up his vanity: “What is worse, I think, is that this East/West dichotomy covers up a deep emptiness in Naipaul the writer, for which Naipaul the social phenomenon is making others pay (127).” On Islamic issues that he sees in Naipaul Said thus succumbs to quite a narrow and personal perspective eclipsing the entire corpus of his aesthetic potentiality as the proof of a Noble writer.

Discovery of the location of vanity in Naipaul is not the end. How gradually and scathingly Said’s observation questions his own reputation as a critic gets more prominence in the book as he grows more impatient and more personal. In another essay entitled ‘Bitter Dispatches from the Third World’ he uses a bestial analogy to elaborate the function of the colonial bent in Naipaul:

To say that Naipaul resembles a scavenger, then, is to say that he now prefers to render the ruins and derelictions of postcolonial history without tenderness...he prefers to indict guerrillas for their pretensions rather than indict the imperialism and social injustice that drove them to insurrection; he attacks Moslems for the wealth of some of their number and for a vague history of African slave trading, thus putting aside many centuries of majority struggle and complex civilization. (116)

Said is obviously very personal of Naipaul and with that he seems to have sympathized the “postcolonial history”, “guerrillas”, “Moslems” and “Africans” which seem to have suffered the Naipaulean attack. But with his careful dehumanization of him in the form of the “scavenger”, an animal that feeds on carrion or dead, the criticism paradoxically turns back to itself. By analogy, if Naipaul is the “scavenger” feeding upon the postcolonial world, by implication the postcolonial world is dead and stinking lifeless carrion. Therefore, what Said has achieved is a suicidal stage; while lampooning Naipaul he also strikes back himself with the same weapon to his own authority of an ethical critic, and obliquely renders the postcolonial world a lifeless entity destined to parish in which, unlike him, Naipaul sees living and aesthetic potentialities. In short, contradictorily he practices the same that he condemns in Naipaul.

Derek Walcottⁱⁱ attempts a poetic humiliation of both Naipaul as person and his works. Through a poem ‘The Mongoose’ to conclude the Calabash Literary Festival in Jamaica, 2008, Derek not only bestializes Naipaul as “mongoose” but also debunks his late fictions (*Half a Life* and *Magic Seeds*) as “dead” so nothing worth full. The following extract of ‘The Mongoose’ poem from *Rhyme and Punishment for Naipaul* by Daniel Trilling is worth quoting here:

I have been *bitten*, I must avoid *infection*
Or else I’ll be as *dead* as Naipaul’s fiction
Read his last novels, you’ll see just
what I mean
A lethargy, approaching the obscene
The model is more ho-hum than Dickens
The essays have more *bite*
They scatter chickens like critics, but
each *stabbing phrase* is *poison*

...

(Uddari 01, emphases added)

The poem is overladen with poison and death related phrases (“bitten,” “infection,” “dead,” “bite,” “stabbing,” and “poison”) pointing to the last works of Naipaul which are supposed to have been bitten

by the mongoose Naipaul. The attack of the poem is largely on Naipaul, and his works are projected as his victims (snakes). In his short reading of the poem that lasts for 5.48 minutes as recorded by Forte C Maximilian he has emphasized on the word “mongoose” more than ten times supplementing it with other phrases like “rodent”, “funny” who cannot be a “friend” to anybody and who excessively takes pride on his own “race.” With reference to “race” Walcott also drags the whole background: Indian origin, history of migration and diasporic situation of Naipaul into condemnation. But, like Said, what is obliquely and even dangerously critiqued in the guise of “mongoose” is the “third world” society that Naipaul represents. The mongoose feeds on venomous snakes like cobra and by analogy the cobra becomes an image of the society that Naipaul explores and represents. In short, while bestializing Naipaul, Walcott also dehumanizes in parallel the societies that he seems to sympathize.

CONCLUSION:

What can be thus concluded from the plethora of estimations of Naipaul is that there are two paradoxical categories of the responses in general in the making of Naipaul as having the attribute of the character Ariel as Mustafa claims. One, as in Bruce King and Rob Nixon, attempts an in-depth analysis of the texts, the intertextuality between the travel writings and fictions, the real world and the textual, history, culture and civilization. In them the works get interpreted, enriched with more meanings and further possibilities and thus achieves the general expectation for them. The other, inconsistent to the first, as has been pointed out in Mohamed Bakari, Edward Said and Derek Walcott is excessively personal with grotesque animal imagery as weapon to lampoon the author. Antagonism runs overwhelmingly high in their readings to baffle and make them lost within. The first enables the potentialities of the texts while the second ignores and bypasses them. Further, within the categories there are sub layers of paradox in that they cancel out each other's claim. Bakari's “gadfly”, Said's “scavenger” and Walcott's “mongoose”, for instance suggest a distinct contempt, a distinct attribute for Naipaul. Lastly, the heterogeneous perceptions also prove paradoxical in that they wrestle between the fictive and the historical, the value of free expression and political correctness. However, irrespective of their becoming either the achieved or the lost responses, what can be claimed is that they are “ethical” in nature; Naipaul has always proved and remained resourceful in the intersection of the both. And not only his writings but also the paradoxical function of the estimations attests his indomitable creative and powerful literary spirit. In this sense, the distinction of Naipaul as Ariel from the Caliban stock of the postcolonial writings by Mustafa is commendable.

END NOTES:

ⁱ John King, " 'A Curiously Colonial Performance': The Eccentric Vision of V. S. Naipaul and J. L. Borges," *The Yearbook of English Studies*, 13 (1983), 232.

ⁱⁱ Walcott was born in Saint Lucia and brought up in Trinidad, a poet and a playwright, the Nobel laureate 1992 and the Professor of Poetry at the University of Essex from 2010 to 2013.

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20. Uddari. "The (Poetic) Clash of the (Literary) Titans: Derek Walcott and VS Naipaul." *Uddari Weblog*, Aug 10, 2018. <https://uddari.wordpress.com/tag/the-mongoose-by-walcott/>.